

STELLAR INITIAL MASS FUNCTION: TRENDS WITH GALAXY MASS AND RADIUS

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Taniya Parikh
and D. Thomas, C. Maraston, K. Westfall,
D. Goddard, S. Meneses-Goytia
+ the MaNGA Collaboration

IMF - σ RELATION

Bottom heavy IMF for more massive galaxies; lensing results inconsistent

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Recent results show massive galaxies with normal IMF

RADIAL VARIATION

Excess of low mass stars only at centres of massive early-types

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Constant IMF for 2 massive galaxies, consistent with Milky Way

Mapping Nearby Galaxies at APO

- Binned spectra radially in elliptical annuli - improve S/N at large R_e and remove sky residuals
- 611 ET galaxies (selected using Galaxy Zoo) with at least one spectrum at $S/N > 7$ in each radial bin
- Split into quintile mass bins: 9 - 11.5 $\log (M/M_{\text{sol}})$

RESULTS

OLD AGES, NEGATIVE Z GRADIENTS

RESULTS

OLD AGES, NEGATIVE Z GRADIENTS

All populations α -enhanced but no radial gradient in $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$

OPTICAL INDICES

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Age, metallicity and α abundance

OPTICAL INDICES

Extra Na required

RESULTS

GRADIENTS

RESULTS

GRADIENTS

+

and additional

RESULTS

SPECTRA

NaI

FeH

RESULTS

IMF-SENSITIVE INDICES

NaI

FeH

RESULTS

IMF-SENSITIVE INDICES

- NaI index profile looks similar to NaD
- Wing-Ford band only shown for $S/N > 100$; exclude highest and lowest mass bins

RESULTS

IMF-SENSITIVE INDICES

- All data points lie at or below models for NaI
- FeH shows positive gradient

RESULTS

IMF-SENSITIVE INDICES

FeH measurement for models with different IMFs

Wing-Ford band - no apparent trend with σ (unlike Na I)

RESULTS

IMF-SENSITIVE INDICES

- All data points lie at or below models for NaI
- FeH shows positive gradient

SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

- Stacked spectra of a total of 611 MaNGA Early Type galaxies were analysed
- Results based on NaI and FeH suggest that a Milky-Way (Kroupa) IMF is sufficient to model the data as a function of mass and radius
- We hope to stretch to more high mass galaxies and attempt to include the Wing-Ford band in the analysis for these

MASS RANGE

Can gain more massive galaxies with lower S/N but this affects the quality of the stacked spectra

Ca4227 and CaT

IMF effects → positive gradient,
 changes in metallicity → negative gradient

EXTRA

TiO1 and TiO2

○	○	8.8 - 9.8	log M/M _⊙
●	●	9.8 - 10.2	
●	●	10.2 - 10.5	
●	●	10.5 - 10.8	
●	●	10.8 - 11.3	

NaI without Na enhancement

- NaD can be affected by interstellar absorption which would affect the derived Na abundance
- Na enhancement would have been overestimated → models would predict weaker NaI

- Kroupa IMF cannot fit the centres of the 3 highest mass bins (Salpeter required)